

Remembering Clifford Beers and Ronald Laing against the borderlinization of lived-experience in contemporary mental health discourse

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Funding: There was no external funding for this work.

Conflicts of interest: The author declares no conflicts of interest. Procedural circumstances bearing on the submission have been disclosed to the editors separately.

Abstract

Recently, an essay on coercive practice in psychiatric settings (Ferreira, 2026) and an opinion on the coming revision of the DSM (Jackman et al., 2026) illustrate a particular framing of "lived-experience" that has become editorially dominant in segments of the mental health literature. We propose that this framing inverts the historical pedigree it claims for itself and obscures the available empirical record. Clifford Beers, whose 1908 testimony founded the modern patient-voice tradition in psychiatry, built institutions in close collaboration with the profession of his moment, and not against it. Ronald Laing, often invoked as a precursor of the "anti-psychiatric" critique, in fact rejected the label which was coined against his consistent wish by David Cooper in 1967, and continued his career as a registered psychiatrist within the European existential-phenomenological tradition until his death. The contemporary lived-experience-expert system, in the form it has assumed, rests on two empirically contested claims: that those who carry lived-experience of mental illness constitute a population external to and structurally opposed to the psychiatric profession, and that patient-centred relational care must be imported into psychiatry from outside. Both claims are at variance with the recorded truth. We introduce the social construct of borderlinization applicable to the publication pattern observed: an institution and group-level drift toward splitting, idealisation, devaluation, and identity diffusion under conditions of suppressed dissenting cultural signalling, in which the cultural surround is recruited into the structure, and a

scapegoat mechanism processes integrating voices through institutional procedures designed for other purposes. We close with a classical-liberal counter, grounded in epistemic pluralism, a scientific evidence base, and voluntary institutional ecology. This is an anti-antipsychiatric argument, and not an anti-critical one.

1. A captured ethos

In successive issues of this journal, two contributions illustrate the shape of an argument that has come to dominate certain quarters of mental health publishing under the banner of lived-experience. Ferreira's essay, "Held but not healed" [1], argues that coercive practice is unsupported by evidence and should be replaced by a "will and preferences" standard derived from an absolutist reading of Article 12 of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) [2]. Jackman and colleagues' opinion, "Revising the DSM-VI" [3], holds that diagnostic classification pathologises "rational responses to injustice" and openly calls for "reform and abolition" of the diagnostic paradigm, citing Mad Studies and decolonial frameworks as relevant innovations. The two pieces were stewarded by the same editor in successive months. The pattern is therefore not incidental but editorial.

Several features of these contributions invite reasoned attention. Ferreira's essay opens with a positionality declaration in which the author identifies herself as holding "relational safety and privilege", a "postgraduate degree", and "professional credibility" as a mental health advocate; she then deploys these explicitly as conditions of legitimate authorship, rather than as disqualifications. This is the structural inverse of the epistemological move the framework borrows from Critical Theory [4, 5]. Where the original framing treated institutional embeddedness as a source of distortion, the contemporary version treats it as the credentialing mechanism. The essay also introduces a temporal caveat: accounts of coercion experienced as beneficial are confined to a pre-2006 period, before the adoption of the CRPD, thereby immunising the framework against historical counterevidence. A coined neologism, "cognitive institutionalisation", performs the work that "false consciousness" once did in earlier critical traditions: it names an internalised disposition that explains why those subject to coercion may nonetheless endorse and submit to it, sounding as a reinterpretation of the Stockholm syndrome.

Jackman et al.'s (2026) [3] piece is more open about pedigree. It cites Mad Studies as a foundational reference; it adopts a 'Global Majority / Minority World' vocabulary derived from decolonial scholarship; it names "sanism" as a discriminatory structure, thus inverting the right-to-treatment legal-advocacy framework in which it was originally developed (we will examine this in detail below);

and it calls explicitly for "abolition" alongside reform. It conflates the legitimate empirical finding of known conflicts of interest among DSM-5-TR task force members [6] with an abolitionist conclusion that does not follow from that premise. Soteria houses, the Power Threat Meaning Framework [7], communal witnessing in faith communities, and Caribbean musical traditions are offered as alternatives. What this combination amounts to, beneath the post-modern vocabulary, is a re-enchantment move: a return to pre-psychiatric modes of meaning-making, dressed in a post-structural atelier.

We do not contest the right of either argument to appear in print. But we do contest the historical claim that the editorial pairing of these papers implicitly advances, which is that this register is what lived-experience has come to mean, or what it ought to mean, in contemporary mental health. Both essays speak as if from a longstanding tradition. They do not.

Their genealogy lies elsewhere. The captured register's intellectual genealogy runs through three converging lines: the Frankfurt School's critique of instrumental reason [4, 5], Foucault's reconstruction of psychiatry as a carceral apparatus [8], and Ivan Illich's reframing of medicine itself as the principal source of population-level iatrogenesis [9].

A note on positionality is in order here, since the framework under examination places considerable burden on the construct. The author writes as an academic and professor of psychiatry and public mental health of some years' standing, trained within the psychodynamic, phenomenological, biopsychosocial and pluralistic, and epidemiological traditions, and, by a circumstance of biography that the framework here discussed would, in its own vocabulary, recognise as lived-experience, also as a clinician who has had the opportunity to know both sides of the consulting room. The dual position is precisely the one we defend, against an editorial register that has tended, of late, to recognise as authentic only those forms of lived-experience compatible with a specific ideological framing. The present essay attempts to recover the author's personally enriched professional stance, and is, in this respect, a defence of a practice to which the author belongs, as much as a critique of an editorial line that has misrepresented it.

2. Psychiatry: Reil's vision and Beers' restructuring of it

Some preliminary deepening of the historical horizon is necessary. The word *psychiatry* was coined in 1808 by Johann Christian Reil (1759–1813), a professor of medicine at the University of Halle, in the short-lived journal "*Beyträge zur Beförderung einer Curmethode auf psychischem Wege*", which he edited with Hoffbauer; the foundational treatise had appeared five years earlier as "*Rhapsodien über die Anwendung der psychischen Curmethode auf Geisteszerrüttungen*" (1803) [10]. Reil

argued that the care of the mentally ill should be neither a sub-branch of medicine, nor of theology, nor of penal practice, but an independent discipline, with its own trained practitioners. He insisted, furthermore, that Psychiatry required the very best of medical practitioners, who ought to meet the patient as *primus inter pares*: first among equals, not subordinates. Reil conceived psychiatry as the meeting of two minds — the mind of the patient and the mind of the physician — with the physician's task being to recognise the pattern as it unfolded, and to do so with compassion [11]. From its inception, the discipline was articulated in a humane register by a man who had described the cortical island that now bears his name and that contemporary neuroscience identifies as a seat of empathy, who had treated his fellow countryman Goethe's renal complaints, and would die five years later, treating soldiers wounded at the Battle of the Nations during the Napoleonic Wars [10]. He was a humanist of the Late Enlightenment age.

In the years immediately preceding the 1808 coining of *Psychiatrie*, the same ethos had produced Philippe Pinel's reforms at Bicêtre (1793) and the Salpêtrière (1795) [12], and his foundational "Traité médico-philosophique sur l'aliénation mentale" (1801) [13]; William Tuke's founding of the York Retreat in 1796 [14, 15]; Vincenzo Chiarugi's "Della pazzia in genere e in specie" (1793–1794) at the Bonifazio hospital in Florence [16]; and Joseph Daquin's "Philosophie de la folie" (1791) at Chambéry [17]. These were not isolated initiatives, but part of the broader Enlightenment commitment articulated philosophically in Kant's "Was ist Aufklärung?" (1784) [18] and politically in the American and French revolutionary bills of rights. Reason, dignity, and autonomy were therefore universal entitlements of the human being, and the mentally ill were not exceptions. Reil's vision of psychiatry as a humane discipline, with practitioners also meeting the patient as *primus inter pares*, is unintelligible apart from this Enlightenment frame. Indeed, the concept of patient autonomy that the contemporary lived-experience-expert system claims to introduce into psychiatry was constitutive of psychiatry's founding moment two centuries earlier.

This historical record contradicts the Michel Foucault reading on which much contemporary critical-theory mental health scholarship rests. Foucault's "Histoire de la folie" (1961) [8] argued that the Enlightenment was the moment of the great confinement and of the medicalisation of madness as a form of social control. The serious historiography of psychiatry, as set by Porter [19], Shorter [20], Goldstein [21], and Scull's revisionist work [22], has, however, documented that the Foucault thesis is empirically unsustainable. The asylum system, with the abuses on which Ferreira (2026) and Jackman et al. (2026) rest, emerged as a nineteenth-century phenomenon, after the Enlightenment psychiatric reformers had done their work, and was in significant respects an institutional betrayal of their commitments rather than their fulfilment (that will be another essay).

The contemporary lived-experience-expert system's implicit historical narrative is not the one supported by historians.

The point now stressed is not a mere archaism. It is that the ethical and dignifying impulse the contemporary lived-experience-expert system claims to be introducing to psychiatry from outside has been internal to the discipline from the moment of its naming. The pre-history of the patient-voice tradition is also, in this respect, the pre-history of the profession itself.

Clifford Whittingham Beers published "*A Mind That Found Itself*" in 1908 [23]. The book is the foundational document of organised patient testimony in modern mental health. It described, in rough and at times devastating detail, the abuses Beers endured during his psychiatric hospitalisation in Connecticut between 1900 and 1903, including physical restraint, neglect, violence by attendants, and the collapse of the institutional environment into a regime of punishment. He was not equivocal about what had been done to him.

The relevant point, however, is what Beers did with that testimony. Within a year of the book's publication and working in collaboration with Adolf Meyer, who was then arguably the most influential American psychiatrist of his generation, and with William James, the father of empirical psychology, who had supplied an endorsing letter for the volume, Beers founded the Connecticut Society for Mental Hygiene in 1908, and the National Committee for Mental Hygiene in 1909 [24, 25]. He devoted the remainder of his life to the reconstruction of institutions in close collaboration with the psychiatric profession he had earlier criticised. The trajectory is the model: lived testimony as the engine of reform, pursued through institutional reconstruction rather than institutional negation. Beers wrote with severity about what he had endured, then worked with the psychiatric profession that had restrained him, in collaboration with Meyer, James, and the next generation of reformers, to change the conditions that had made the abuses possible. He did not call for abolition. He called for better hospitals, for trained personnel, for scientific investigation of mental illness, and for the dignification of patient testimony as evidence within psychiatric reasoning.

Beers' achievements occurred at the same time that American medical education was undergoing the Flexner reform [26], reinstating the academic, humanistic, non-utilitarian vision of medicine that Reil had fought for and lost a century earlier in the Prussian public health system [27, 28].

This is not the pedigree the captured discourse of the contemporary lived-experience-expert system claims when it invokes lived-experience. The Beers register is reformist, collaborative, and institution-building. Its central commitment is that the testimony of those who have suffered psychiatric harm enters the deliberative process *with* psychiatric knowledge in productive tension, and not *against* it as a substitute. The contemporary register inverts this. Lived-experience is

repositioned as an autonomous epistemology that displaces clinical knowledge, with formal CRPD-based legal frameworks operationalising the displacement. Ferreira's (2026) essay states the inversion plainly: "Recognising lived-experience as a valid epistemology does not reject clinical knowledge or research expertise; it rebalances whose knowledge is legitimised, supported, and afforded authority" [1]. The verb may be *'rebalances'*, but the structural commitment is replacement, or abolition, as Jackman et al. (2026) unapologetically put it [3]. The lived-expert movement, which begins with Beers and arrives at the abolition register, has not extended its tradition. It has terminated it.

3. The clinician's lived-experience and the wounded healer

The lived-experience-expert system rests, in its present form, on a constituency claim. The claim is that those who carry a lived-experience of mental illness constitute a distinct population, external to and structurally opposed to the psychiatric profession, whose voice has been excluded from professional deliberation and now requires admission. The claim is foundational to the rhetorical force of the contemporary movement-system and, on the available evidence, also false.

Approximately one in three psychiatrists has a personal history of mental illness, according to repeated surveys. A Canadian cohort of psychiatry residents reported the figure at 33%, with 36.8% citing career implications as the principal barrier to disclosure [29]. A multicentre European study of 4,245 psychiatrists across 32 countries acknowledged, with effect sizes in the range of $d = -0.88$ to -0.92 , that the lived-experience of mental illness in psychiatrists is significantly associated with reduced stigmatising attitudes toward patients [30], rendering the dual role one of the strongest known clinician-side modifiers of stigma in the literature. The German EKB study found over 80% of mental health professionals reporting lived-experience of mental crisis or disorder [31]. Victor and colleagues (2022) reported 80% of mental health professionals have a history of mental health struggles, and nearly half are currently diagnosed [32]. The constituency the contemporary movement claims to represent overlaps in considerable measure with the profession it claims to correct.

The historical lineage is older still. Jung formalised the figure of the wounded healer within his Collected Works in the 1950s, drawing on the Chiron myth and making the analyst's susceptibility to influence constitutive of the analytic relationship, "you can exert no influence if you are not susceptible to influence" [33]. The training analysis, which is the institutionalised requirement that the analyst undergo their own depth analysis before treating others, has been a structural feature of psychoanalytic education since the 1920s and represents the profession's earliest formal

recognition that clinical competence rests in part on the clinician's own confrontation with psychological suffering. Nouwen extended the archetype into pastoral care in *"The Wounded Healer"* (1972) [34]. The construct was developed empirically by, among others, Sedgwick [35] and Zerubavel & Wright [36].

The figures whose work shaped psychiatry and psychotherapy were not, as a matter of historical record, absent from the suffering they approached or treated. William James described his own depressive crisis in *The Varieties of Religious Experience* (1902) [37]. Freud's self-analysis through correspondence with Fliess (1895–1900) is foundational to psychoanalytic method [38]. Jung's "confrontation with the unconscious" (1913–1917), documented retrospectively in *The Red Book* and in *Memories, Dreams, Reflections* (1962), formed the basis for his subsequent clinical theory [39, 40]. Bion's early Northfield experiments arose in part from his own war trauma [41]; Winnicott [42], Kohut [43], and Ferenczi [44] developed their clinical theorising in productive relation to their personal analyses and documented depressive episodes.

The paradigm cases in contemporary mental health are well-documented. Kay Redfield Jamison, Dalio Family Professor in Mood Disorders at the Johns Hopkins School of Medicine and co-author of the standard textbook *Manic-Depressive Illness* [45], disclosed her own bipolar I disorder in *"An Unquiet Mind"* (1995) [46]. Marsha Linehan, Professor of Psychology at the University of Washington and the developer of dialectical behaviour therapy, disclosed in 2011 that she had been hospitalised at the age of seventeen for over two years with severe self-harm and chronic suicidality, having been initially misdiagnosed with schizophrenia, and that she had vowed during the hospitalisation "to get myself out of hell and then go back and get others out" [47, 48]; DBT was developed from that vow. Patricia Deegan, Frederick Frese, and Daniel Fisher built the recovery and consumer/survivor movements from within professional psychology and psychiatry, drawing on personal histories of psychosis [49]. Elyn Saks, Professor of Law, Psychology, and Psychiatry at the University of Southern California, published *"The Center Cannot Hold"* (2007) [50] on her own lithium-managed schizophrenia. Linda Gask, Professor Emerita of Primary Care Psychiatry at Manchester, published *"The Other Side of Silence"* (2015) [51] on her own depression.

Contemporary institutional training within the profession has crystallised this dual role. The Royal College of Psychiatrists' Lived-Experience Network operates under its Culture of Care Programme [52]. Even if controversial in mainstream psychiatry, the Critical Psychiatry Network in the United Kingdom, which includes Joanna Moncrieff, Sami Timimi, Pat Bracken, Philip Thomas, Duncan Double, and Hugh Middleton, has for over twenty-five years pursued a sustained critique of so-

called 'biomedical dominance' from within the profession, and has published this critique in mainstream psychiatric journals [53].

The substantive consequence of all this for the present argument is that the rhetorical force of the lived-experience-expert system and movement depends on a legacy claim that the published literature contradicts. The constituency it purports to represent is heavily integrated within the profession, has been so for over a century in formal recognition, and has produced some of the most consequential clinical innovations of the modern era. The contemporary lived-experience expert system and movement do not represent the admission of a once-excluded voice into the deliberative arena. They represent one specific ideological framing of that voice, whose claim to speak for the entire constituency is contested by, among others, the clinicians within the profession who carry lived-experience and have integrated it into their clinical work without arriving at abolitionist conclusions. The Beers–Laing–Jamison tradition, in which lived-experience strengthens clinical work rather than displacing it, is rendered invisible by an editorial register that gatekeeps which forms of disclosure count as authentic.

4. First-person authority, properly bounded

The captured register presupposes a particular reading of first-person authority, namely the classical philosophical articulation by Davidson [54] and the extensive development by Moran [55] and Bilgrami [56], that an individual's reports about their own mental states carry an epistemic privilege not shared by third-person attributions. The position is real and well-defended in the analytic philosophical literature. Phenomenological psychopathology in the Jaspers tradition rests on it, as does the descriptive seriousness Laing demanded of his own discipline, and the patient-voice tradition we have traced from Beers onwards would not have meaning without it. We do not contest the concept. What we contest is its absolutisation: the conversion of a properly bounded epistemic privilege into a sovereign authority that cannot be qualified, contextualised, or supplemented by third-person clinical reasoning.

The philosophical literature carefully distinguishes several authority claims that the captured register tends to conflate. We name five.

The **phenomenological authority** resides in what the experience is like, its qualitative texture, its felt presence, and its lived shape, and is reported by the person who undergoes it with an epistemic privilege that no external observer can approximate. This is the core of Jaspers' descriptive psychopathology, what Sims has called the discipline of attending to the experiential structure of the conditions that psychiatric language names, and what contemporary phenomenological

psychiatry, in the tradition of Stanghellini, has continued to develop [57]. Phenomenological authority is strong and uncontested by any serious approach within psychiatry.

The **volitional authority** – what the person wants, prefers, intends, or values – is, in the classical case, more reliably reported by the person than by anyone else. The legitimate territory of the CRPD's "will and preferences" formulation rests here. Volitional authority is strong, with documented limits: the limits occur in conditions of impaired capacity as, for example, in cases of psychotic disorganisation, severe affective episodes, advanced dementia, acute intoxication, in conditions of coercive social pressure that distorts preference formation, and in conditions where the person lacks the conceptual resources to articulate what they actually want. The capacity-based legal tradition is the proper response to these documented limits; the absolutist CRPD reading erases them.

The **causal authority** – why one feels, thinks, or behaves as one does – is not, on the available evidence, reliably reported by the person. Almost the entirety of the psychoanalytic tradition, much of cognitive-behavioural science, and the empirical literature on confabulation and unconscious motivation presuppose that first-person reports of causation are systematically unreliable. The clinical encounter, properly conducted, is in part the careful joint examination of causal hypotheses that the patient cannot supply unaided.

The **diagnostic authority** – whether one has the condition, the clinical encounter would identify – is partially available to the patient, the privileged reporter of phenomenology, and partially not: recognition of one's own condition requires conceptual resources, comparative perspective, and integration of phenomenology with biological and behavioural correlates that the patient typically does not bring to the encounter unaided. Diagnostic authority is shared, and the sharing is asymmetric in a direction the captured discourse refuses to acknowledge.

The **policy authority** regarding what shape psychiatric care should take at the institutional and societal levels is not a matter to which first-person experience confers privileged authority of any kind. It is a public deliberation question to which patient testimony contributes, alongside epidemiological evidence, clinical experience, ethical reasoning, and legal-institutional analysis, with no presumption of sovereignty for any single contributor. The conflation of phenomenological and volitional authority (which the patient genuinely has) with policy authority (which no one has on first-person grounds alone) is the philosophical move that does the heaviest lifting in the captured register.

The shift from the first two authority claims to the latter two is the philosophical error underlying the structural anomaly documented so far. It is what permits the captured register to treat the

abolitionist policy conclusion as if it followed from the patient's first-person testimony, when in fact it requires institutional, empirical, and ethical premises that first-person authority cannot supply. The Birnbaum–Perlin original sense of *sanism* was the legitimate critique of clinicians who failed to take phenomenological and volitional authority seriously. The contemporary lived-experience system-movement deployment claims diagnostic and policy authority on the same epistemic ground, which is precisely the move that the philosophical literature does not allow.

Beers and Laing are exemplars of properly bounded authority. Beers held absolute authority over what had been done to him, both phenomenological and volitional, and deferred to Meyer and James on questions of institutional reform; the partnership worked because the authority was correctly scoped. Laing's phenomenological psychopathology took the patient's first-person report with utmost seriousness, while remaining fully within the discipline of psychiatric reasoning on causal and diagnostic questions. The legacy we are recovering is not one that denies first-person authority. It is one that knows how to bound it.

5. Laing against "antipsychiatry"

The second undisputed figure whose name circulates as a precursor of the contemporary lived-experience system-movement is Ronald David Laing. The attribution of anti-psychiatrist stands in need of correction. The term '*antipsychiatry*' was coined by David Cooper in 1967, in "*Psychiatry and Anti-Psychiatry*" [58]. Cooper coined it in part to describe his own work, and that of his collaborators, including Laing, at the Philadelphia Association. Laing's response, documented across the remainder of his career, was rejection. He disliked the label; he repudiated it in interviews; and he continued to identify as a psychiatrist working within an existential-phenomenological tradition until his death in 1989 [59, 60].

The substance of Laing's position is easily misread, because his early reception in the 1960s counterculture treated him as an emancipatory figure. The texts do not support that reading without qualification [61]: "*The Divided Self*" (1960) [62] is, in its primary intellectual lineage, a work of phenomenological psychopathology in the tradition of Jaspers [63], Binswanger [64], Minkowski [65], and Merleau-Ponty [66]. Its central argument, that the experience of psychosis can be entered, understood, and rendered intelligible through patient and disciplined phenomenological attention, is continuous with Jaspers' *General Psychopathology* and Andrew Sims' contemporary descriptive psychopathology [63, 67]. Laing was not arguing that schizophrenia did not exist, nor that psychiatric knowledge was illegitimate. He was arguing that the existing psychiatric knowledge of

his moment had failed to attend phenomenologically to the experiential structure of those conditions, and that this failure had consequences for care.

He remained a registered medical practitioner. He treated patients. He worked within institutions, including those he himself founded, such as Kingsley Hall, which was an experiment in residential care rather than a negation of care. Most importantly for the present argument, he distinguished himself sharply from the abolitionist register that emerged around the term Cooper had created. In interviews late in his life, he reflected with visible irritation on the persistent attachment of the "antipsychiatry" label to him, against his own consistent rejection of it, and on the misunderstanding of his work by those who had taken the label up [59].

This matters because Ferreira's (2026) essay, without naming him, hands the R.D. Laing tradition its clearest contemporary illustration, only to render it invisible within her own framework. Recounting a moment during involuntary medication when she became visibly distressed, she writes that her clinician "paused, made eye contact, and acknowledged my distress... I was treated not as a problem to be managed, but as a human being experiencing fear, and the impact of that interaction has endured to this day" [1]. This is, with no modification required, what Laing and Sims would call good clinical psychiatric care. It is phenomenological attention to lived distress within an institutional encounter that the contemporary lived-experience framework otherwise codes as wholly coercive. Her essay cannot name what the clinician did because the clinician practised psychiatry well, and the Ferreira framework requires that psychiatry be the problem. The anecdote is, in consequence, offered as an exception to the institutional logic, rather than as a constitutive instance of it. The Laing tradition would read it the other way: the clinician's pause was simply psychiatry, and the framework that cannot recognise it has lost the discipline.

6. Borderlinization as a social construct and capture mechanism

We propose *borderlinization* as a mirroring social construct for the structural pattern visible in the captured editorial register. The term names a predictable institution- and group-level drift toward splitting, identity diffusion, and idealisation and devaluation that emerges when dissenting or at-variance cultural signals are systematically suppressed. The clinical analogy is to borderline personality structure as classically described, but the deployment is at the institution and group level, and not at the individual level. The ethical grounding is deterministic in the tradition of Schopenhauer and Sapolsky [68]: the individual exhibiting the structure is not culpable; the suppressive social surround is the pathogenic variable; and the appropriate response is analytic rather than condemnatory.

Applied to the editorial pattern under examination, the diagnostic structure resolves cleanly. First, *splitting*, whereby psychiatry is rendered as a pure oppressor system on the one hand, and as the relational care of Ferreira's clinician on the other, with no integrating account of how these can be aspects of one and the same discipline. Second, *idealisation and devaluation*, whereby Soteria, Power Threat Meaning, communal witnessing, Caribbean musical traditions, and faith-community support are idealised, while institutional psychiatric knowledge, diagnostic classification, pharmacological treatment, and clinical authority are devalued. The contents of each pole are presented as if they belong to non-overlapping categories, when in fact considerable empirical and conceptual continuity exists between them. Third, *identity diffusion at the author level*, since the contributors to both essays are institutionally credentialed leaders writing in elite open-access journals, holding positions at universities and within international advocacy networks, yet positioning themselves discursively as voices from the margin. This is not deception, but the structural confusion that the borderlinizing process predicts. Fourth, *recruitment of the surround* in the editorial space at international journals, United Nations frameworks (the CRPD General Comment No. 1 reading [2]), World Health Organization guidance, non-governmental advocacy infrastructure, and academic critical-theory departments together form a cultural surround that, having been recruited into the structure, no longer functions as an external check upon it. Critique from outside is parsed as the structure predicts, as further evidence of the social construct being identified.

The classical phenomenological criterion of *sharedness*, which has historically distinguished cultural belief from delusion, misfires under these conditions. When the cultural surround is itself organised around the structure of the belief system, sharedness no longer indexes reality-testing; it indexes capture.

The scapegoat mechanism as the fifth element

A fifth structural feature follows from the four above-described. Splitting at population level requires the "all bad" pole to be borne by identifiable individuals, the scapegoat function described by authors including Melanie Klein on projective identification [69], Wilfred Bion on basic-assumption groups [70], René Girard on the foundational role of the surrogate victim [71], and Vamik Volkan on the chosen-trauma and chosen-enemy dynamics of large groups [72]. When the cultural surround has been recruited into the borderlinizing structure, the institutional mechanisms available to it, such as formal complaints to employers, professional society referrals, social media campaigns, journal retraction efforts, and departmental inquiries, serve as the operational arm of the

scapegoating process. They reassign the dissenting voice from the deliberative process to the disposable category.

This mechanism is particularly precise in selecting its objects. The psychiatric academic who can demonstrate that the discipline contains *both* the relational care the captured discourse coopts as exceptional *and* the institutional force it identifies as constitutive is the figure who most threatens the splitting with integration. Integration would dissolve the structure. Scapegoating disarms the threat by reassigning the integrating voice to the "all bad" pole. The pattern has become visible in a series of recent controversies: the institutional treatment of Allen Frances following his sustained public critique of the DSM-5 development process [73]; the professional consequences for clinicians whose empirical conclusions aligned with the Cass Review in the United Kingdom [74]; or more recently, in Australia, AHPRA imposed analogous restrictions on Andrew Amos in February 2026 [75, 76]. The pattern is consistent: the dissenting voice is not engaged by the profession's deliberative structures because such engagement would require the discipline to integrate what the borderlinizing structure has split. It is processed through the institutional structures that perform the scapegoating function on behalf of the borderlinizing system.

It is worth observing here a recursive characteristic of the mechanism in its present configuration, which we have come, in part through personal acquaintance, to regard as structural and not as incidental. The captured editorial register produces a discourse in which substantive academic dissent finds the deliberative channels themselves closed, either by reviewer-network capture, by editorial line, or by the gatekeeping function of the journals in question. The dissent is therefore displaced onto the digital media, where its expression takes on the affective shape characteristic of those media: ironic, sharp, occasionally caustic, what may be termed the register of the epistemic-guerrillero. The captured apparatus then harvests that displaced expression as the material it requires for the formal complaint, the professional society referral, the social-media campaign, and the journal-level retraction request. The dissenting voice is, in consequence, processed through institutional procedures rather than engaged through deliberative ones. The provocation, on this analysis, is not an unwanted side-effect of the discourse, but a structural requirement of it: the scapegoat function presupposes a target acting out in the displaced register, and the displacement is itself produced by the closure of the deliberative one. The mechanism is, in this respect, self-completing.

The point is not that critics of psychiatry should be immune from professional accountability. Rather, it is that the institutional infrastructure of accountability, including complaint procedures, professional society referrals, and employer pressure, has been recruited into a function for which

those procedures were not designed. The borderlinizing structure converts deliberative scrutiny into an expulsion ritual, or cancellation.

Vocabulary as a further locus of inversion

The captured register additionally depends on a vocabulary that performs the work that "false consciousness" did in earlier critical traditions: it names internalised dispositions that explain why those subject to coercion may nonetheless endorse it. The vocabulary is heterogeneous in provenance. Some terms, such as "cognitive institutionalisation", coined by Ferreira herself, are recent neologisms invented for this purpose. Two others, "sanism", devised by Birnbaum in 1960 [77] and developed by Perlin from 1980 [78, 79], and Fricker's "epistemic injustice" (2007) [80] have legitimate academic genealogies in legal scholarship and analytic philosophy, respectively, and are deployed in the captured discourse in ways that depart from their originators' frameworks, in the case of *sanism*, by direct inversion. *Sanism*, in its original Birnbaum-Perlin sense, developed within a right-to-treatment legal-advocacy framework: Morton Birnbaum, the term's originator, was the architect of the right-to-treatment doctrine for psychiatric patients and a defender of humane involuntary care under procedural safeguards, not its abolitionist opponent. The contemporary Mad Studies deployment turns the term against the very treatment-rights tradition from which it derives. The pattern of inversion that we identify in the cases of Beers and Laing is, in this respect, also visible at the level of vocabulary itself. This is not a condition akin to Nick Haslam's *concept creep* [81] but something else and the reverse of it; it is the borderlinization construct operating at the language and meaning level.

It may be useful to state what follows next in plain terms, as this analysis requires.

What is taking place in this segment of the mental health literature, meaning, the contemporary lived-experience system-movement, is the absorption of an inherited critical-theory tradition into the editorial and institutional infrastructure of academic publishing. The tradition has a documented lineage: the Frankfurt School, French post-structuralism, the post-1968 academic reception of these, the conjunction in the 1990s with identity politics and decolonial scholarship, and the institutionalisation since approximately 2010 through journals, funders, professional society statements, and patient-advocacy organisations now functioning as funded actors with editorial reach. Jackman et al. (2026) [3] name the lineage themselves when they cite Mad Studies and decolonial work. Ferreira (2026) [1] does not name the pedigree but reproduces its grammar with fidelity: positionality, epistemic injustice, the displacement of objective standards by experiential ones, and the absolutist human-rights reading. To name this legacy accurately is not a hostile act, nor does it require the polemical vocabulary in which it is sometimes carried out

elsewhere. It requires acknowledgement that the editorial pattern at this journal, and at others, represents a substantive intellectual commitment rather than a neutral elevation of voice. The borderlinizing structure, including its scapegoat function and its vocabulary capture, follows from the commitment.

We make no claim that the individuals involved are unaware, dishonest, or motivated by anything other than the dignity of those who have suffered psychiatric harm. The deterministic frame holds. What is claimed is that the structure has the predicted form and that this form is incompatible with the historical and empirical lineage of lived-experience that the discourse claims to inherit.

7. Individual clinical limit-setting and the public arena: deafening silence

The construct of borderlinization, as we have laid it out in the preceding section, names a structural pattern at the institutional and group level. The clinical literature on borderline structure at the individual level is, by contrast, substantial and well-developed. Otto Kernberg has provided the canonical structural framework for borderline personality organisation since the 1960s, with his emphasis on the structural interview, the maintenance of the treatment frame, and the disciplined setting of limits as core technical tasks [82]. Heinz Kohut, from the self-psychological tradition, emphasised empathic immersion in the patient's subjective experience and the use of the self-object transference as the channel through which integration can be achieved [83]. Subsequent contributions by John Gunderson [84], Marsha Linehan [85], and Anthony Bateman and Peter Fonagy [86] have refined the clinical apparatus, each within a different theoretical stem but converging on a common principle: borderline structure at the individual scale requires a containing frame, the maintenance of clinical limits, the discipline of staying with the here-and-now of the encounter, and the patient cultivation of an integrating perspective.

Writing from a position trained in psychodynamics but outside the psychoanalytic tradition strictly understood, we have found in clinical practice that the combination of limits-setting in the Kernberg sense and empathic engagement with the here-and-now in the Kohutian sense is, for the practitioner who is not a psychoanalyst, a sufficient and usable synthesis for the clinical encounter at the individual scale. The discipline knows what to do with the structure when it presents in the consulting room. It has codified the procedures, taught them through training programmes, and developed empirical evidence of their efficacy across psychotherapeutic modalities and even in streamlined medical management.

At the social-discursive scale at which borderlinization presents in the contemporary captured register, the discipline has no analogous code, no analogous training, no analogous mode of

engagement. Editorial committees do not receive Kernberg training in limits-setting at the level of journal stewardship. Professional bodies have not developed Kohut protocols for empathic immersion in the perspectives of dissenting colleagues. The clinical wisdom that the discipline has accumulated for individual borderline encounters has no institutional analogue for the structural-discursive form of the same pattern. Where the individual encounter has Kernberg, Kohut, Linehan, and Bateman-Fonagy, the social encounter has nothing comparable at the level of the discipline. The discipline has not addressed itself, in any sustained or codified manner, to the question of how its institutions should engage with the structural pattern of borderlinization at the scale at which the pattern now operates.

This absence is consequential. It validates the construct of borderlinization itself, establishes a need that has yet to be met, and produces a predictable result. The clinician who recognises the structure at the social-discursive level, but who has no disciplined channel through which to engage it, finds the deliberative organs of the profession closed to substantive dissent, either by editorial line, by reviewer-network capture, or by the gatekeeping function of the institutions in question. The clinician then, in our experience and in the experience of colleagues in analogous positions, defaults to the digital register, where expression takes on the affective shape characteristic of those media: ironic, sharp, occasionally caustic. This displaced expression is then harvested as the material the institutional scapegoat function requires. In clinical vocabulary, the dynamic is one of acting-out with elements of displacement, in the sense Vaillant has catalogued in his defensive-operations taxonomy: the impulse for which no containing frame is available is discharged through an alternative channel, and the alternative channel is then read as evidence of the 'pathology' rather than as evidence of the missing frame [87].

The consequence is therefore not a character failing of the dissenting clinician; it is a predictable structural outcome of the discipline's failure to develop, at social and institutional scale, the engagement tools it has developed with such care at individual scale. The recovery of the patient-led tradition we have argued for in the preceding sections, we propose, also requires the development of a disciplined disciplinary frame for engagement with borderlinization at the scale at which it now manifests in the editorial and institutional life of the field. This is a constructive task, and not a polemical one. The discipline owes itself the development of such a frame, and the present essay is offered, in part, as a contribution to its initiation.

8. The therapeutic alliance and the ethics of the profession

The second rhetorical move on which the captured discourse depends is the implication that patient-centred, relational, dignity-respecting care must be imported into psychiatry from outside the profession. Ferreira's (2026) [1] essay positions her clinician's relational pause as an exception within an institutional logic that is otherwise coded as wholly coercive. Jackman et al.'s (2026) [3] piece treats the recognition of patient dignity as the contribution of community-based alternatives whose conceptual ancestry lies outside the diagnostic profession. In both cases, the substantive commitment that the patient is a partner, and not an object, is presented as something the profession must learn from outside. This too misreads the existing history.

The therapeutic alliance has been the most consistently replicated predictor of psychotherapy outcome across modalities over the past three decades [88, 89]. The conceptual lineage begins with Freud's *Dynamics of Transference* (1912), in which the patient's capacity for collaborative therapeutic engagement is distinguished from transference manifestations [90]. Sterba (1934) developed the alliance between the analyst and the patient's rational ego [91]. Zetzel (1956) coined the term "therapeutic alliance" as a distinct concept [92]. Menninger (1958) developed the therapeutic contract [93]; Greenson (1965, 1967) distinguished the therapeutic alliance from the working alliance and from the real relationship [94]. Bordin (1979) developed the pan-theoretical model, which relies on agreement on goals, assignment of tasks, and the development of bonds, and remains the most widely cited alliance framework in the literature [95]. Rogers (1957) had independently articulated the humanistic parallel in the core conditions of effective therapy [96]. Horvath and Symonds (1991), and the subsequent Horvath, Del Re, Flückiger and Symonds meta-analysis (2011), confirmed the empirical centrality of the alliance: it accounts for approximately 7.5% of psychotherapy outcome variance, and outperforms specific technique in most direct comparisons [89, 97]. Wampold's contextual model and Norcross's APA Division 29 reviews have placed this finding at the centre of contemporary outcome research [98, 99].

The empirical centre of psychotherapy has been relational for forty years. It is taught in every accredited psychiatric and psychological training programme worldwide. The framing that the profession requires instruction in relational care from outside misrepresents the existing curriculum.

The codified ethical structure is older still. The Hippocratic tradition placed patient welfare at the centre of medical practice [100]. The Declaration of Geneva (WMA, 1948) [101], the Declaration of Helsinki (1964) [102], the American Psychiatric Association's *Principles of Medical Ethics with Annotations Especially Applicable to Psychiatry* (continuously revised since 1973) [103], and Beauchamp and Childress's *Principles of Biomedical Ethics* [104] articulate the undisputed ethical

and deontological commitments of the profession – non-maleficence, beneficence, autonomy, justice – which the contemporary lived-experience system-movement claims as its own contribution.

The international psychiatric profession produced its peculiar ethical reckoning in direct response to documented abuses within it. The Declaration of Hawaii (WPA, 1977) was drafted in the wake of Soviet psychiatric repression of political and religious dissidents, after the World Psychiatric Association had been pressed by member societies to investigate the allegations [105]. The Declaration of Madrid (WPA, 1996) [106] extended the scope of the framework to euthanasia, torture, and the death penalty, with mandatory ratification by all 145 member societies under threat of expulsion. The Madrid Declaration affirms, in a language adopted in 1996, a decade before the United Nations CRPD and three decades before the contemporary lived-experience-expert system-movement, that "the patient should be accepted as a partner by right in the therapeutic process, that the therapist-patient relationship must be based on mutual trust and respect to allow the patient to make free and informed decisions". The WPA Code of Ethics (2020) [107] develops the structure across clinical, educational, research, and public mental health domains.

The formulation *partner by right*, adopted in 1996, anticipates the substantive commitment that the contemporary lived-experience-expert system-movement claims to introduce to the profession. The profession committed itself to this thirty years ago, through its own deliberative structures, in direct response to ethical reckoning prompted by documented abuses. The captured discourse acts as though this had not happened.

Patient advocacy as an internal psychiatric tradition is older still, and considerably older than the contemporary lived-experience-expert system movement that claims to introduce it. The pedigree, as above exposed, runs from Reil, who coined the discipline in 1808 and demanded that its practitioners be of the very best, meeting the patient as *primus inter pares* [10]; through Pinel at Bicêtre (1793) [12], Tuke at the York Retreat (1796) [14, 15], Rush in America [108], Dorothea Dix in collaboration with the psychiatric profession of her day [109], Beers with Meyer and James in 1908–1909 [23-25], the Northfield experiments under Bion and Rickman (1942–43) [110], Maxwell Jones at Mill Hill and Henderson [111], Tom Main's "*The Ailment*" (1957) [112], Franco Basaglia's "*L'istituzione negata*" (1968) [113] and Italian Law 180 (1978) [114], Caplan's *Principles of Preventive Psychiatry* (1964) [115], Anthony's articulation of the recovery vision (1993) [116], and the present-day Critical Psychiatry Network [117], each represents internal psychiatric reform driven by professional commitment to patient dignity (and, in Tuke's case, by lay reform that the discipline then absorbed and developed).

None of these figures required instruction in the necessity of advocacy from outside the discipline.

The substantive commitments the captured discourse claims to introduce are not novel: patient partnership, relational care, dignity, informed decision-making, and advocacy against coercive practice. Each is already inscribed in the empirical psychotherapy literature, in the codified ethics of the international psychiatric profession, and in the documented historical tradition of internal psychiatric reform. The distinctive contribution of the contemporary lived-experience system-movement is therefore not the commitments themselves, but the framing that operationalises them through abolition of the diagnostic paradigm and through the replacement of capacity-based intervention with an absolute-autonomy framework under the CRPD General Comment No. 1 reading, a framing that the empirical and ethical traditions did not endorse, and which they, in many cases, explicitly rejected [118-120].

The contemporary lived-experience system-movement did not introduce patient-centred psychiatric care; the claims of authorship are produced by erasing the profession's own.

9. The classical-liberal counter

The alternative proposed here is not the restoration of a 'biomedical' monopoly; the 'biomedical' wording, properly applied to a register of research into biological mechanisms, is sometimes used as a characterisation of psychiatric clinical practice in toto, which is the kind of category move the captured discourse exploits. Neither the Beers nor the R.D. Laing legacy endorsed biomedical monopoly, and the present essay does not endorse it either. The alternative is evidence-based, best-practice institutional pluralism, enforced not by an editorial line but by voluntary association and exit rights.

The relevant intellectual reference is Paul Feyerabend's "*Against Method*" [121], whose epistemic-anarchist argument holds that scientific knowledge advances through the genuine plurality of incommensurable approaches rather than through the imposition of a single methodological orthodoxy. Feyerabend's argument concerned, however, the *generation* of scientific knowledge, and not its clinical *deployment* in the care of vulnerable persons. Translated to the mental health field, the principle requires careful differentiation. At the level of academic inquiry and conceptual development, the discipline is served by a plurality of approaches in an environment of epistemic competition. At the level of clinical deployment, the criterion is empirical evidence or, where evidence is incomplete, the discipline's best-practice consensus. Core treatments meeting these criteria are not optional; they are owed to the patient. Complementary approaches, such as peer-led services, faith-based supports, Soteria-style residential alternatives, and other traditional

cultural forms of meaning-making, can be legitimate additions to the ecology of care, but not substitutes for the evidence-based core. Alternative frameworks that displace evidence-based treatment even when the evidence supports it, for example, abolitionist proposals that suggest removing pharmacological treatment for psychosis from clinical practice, or absolutist autonomy frameworks that withdraw capacity-based interventions from crisis care, are not part of the pluralism the present essay defends. They are constrained monism in a 'pluralist' vocabulary.

The classical-liberal correlate is the institutional ecology defended in the tradition of Nozick [122], and earlier in John Stuart Mill: the recognition that legitimate institutional plurality requires *exit rights* as the operative criterion [123]. A peer-run respite that can be entered and left freely is a legitimate addition to the ecology of care. A diagnostic-abolitionist framework operationalised through CRPD-based legal change that removes the option of capacity-based intervention from those who would, in fact, have wished it under conditions of crisis is not a contribution to plurality but a removal of an option. The framework Ferreira (2026) [1] and Jackman et al (2026) [3] advance describes itself as pluralistic, but operates monistically: it seeks the global replacement of one set of legal and clinical structures by another.

The classical-liberal point is that the actual coercion under examination here is not the coercion of individual patients by individual clinicians, which is real, sometimes harmful, and rightly criticised following the Beers register. The actual coercion is the editorial and institutional capture that forecloses the legitimate plurality of approaches by enforcing a single discursive register as the condition of professional respectability, and that activates the scapegoat mechanism against those who insist on the empirical and historical record. The present essay is itself an attempt to test whether that capture has yet become complete.

10. What uncaptured lived expertise looks like

What does uncaptured lived expertise look like? It looks like Beers' writing "*A Mind That Found Itself*" and then spending forty years building institutions with the profession he had criticised. It looks like Jamison co-authoring the standard textbook on bipolar disorder while disclosing in "*An Unquiet Mind*" the disorder she lives with. It looks like Linehan developing dialectical behaviour therapy out of her own hospitalisation and her vow to come back for the others. It looks like the clinician in Ferreira's anecdote – who paused, made eye contact, and acknowledged her fear and distress – and like the Laing–Jaspers phenomenological stem that taught psychiatry to value that pause as a clinical act. It looks like advance directives and crisis planning developed jointly by patients and clinicians, with the option of capacity-based intervention preserved as part of the ecology of care

rather than abolished as a categorical wrong. It looks like Soteria houses, faith-community support, peer-run respites, and traditional psychiatric inpatient units co-existing as voluntary options, when not contraindicated, rather than competing for a monopoly.

What it does not look like is the editorial pattern this essay has examined. Two essays in successive months at this journal, one calling explicitly for "abolition" of the diagnostic paradigm, the other for the systemic elimination of the substituted decision-making framework that has historically permitted intervention in psychiatric crisis, were both stewarded as if they represented the consensus of the lived-experience constituency, rather than one specific ideological inheritance within it. The constituency, in fact, contains the Beers-style reformer, the Laing-style charismatic phenomenologist, the Jamison-style brave dual-role clinician, the patient who found involuntary admission distressing, the patient who found it lifesaving, the survivor who supports CRPD absolutism, and the survivor who regards it as the legalisation of preventable suicide. The editorial line currently audible at this journal accommodates one slice of that constituency and treats the others as instances of false consciousness, so-called *cognitive institutionalisation*, in the Ferreira (2026) essay's own term, or, increasingly, as objects for the scapegoat function.

The present essay is offered as an instance of the constituency that is not currently being heard, in this editorial environment.

Conclusion

The present argument has rested on four lines of work: historical evidence, empirical evidence, social analysis, and a constructive proposal.

From an historiographical standpoint, the legacy that runs from Reil and Beers through Laing to community psychiatry, and from there to Jamison, Linehan, and the contemporary clinician constituency, does not terminate in the contemporary lived-experience-expert system-movement. That movement represents a substantive intellectual commitment of its own, with a distinct footprint in Critical Theory, in post-structural and decolonial scholarship, and in Mad Studies. A claim upon the historical figures cannot be sustained by inverting their commitments.

Empirically, we have demonstrated that the constituency of lived-experience overlaps substantially with psychiatrists themselves, as confirmed by repeated and extended surveys; that the therapeutic alliance has been the most replicated predictor of psychotherapy outcome for more than thirty years; and that the international psychiatric profession committed itself to patient partnership as a right in its 1996 ethical code.

In social analysis, we have identified a structural pattern in the captured discourse and named it borderlinization: a social construct whose elements include splitting, idealisation and devaluation, identity diffusion, recruitment of the cultural surround, the scapegoat mechanism, and the capture of vocabulary itself, all under conditions of suppressed dissenting cultural signalling. The discipline of psychiatry possesses, at the clinical individual scale, codified procedures and traditions for engaging with borderline structure; at the social and institutional scale, relevant for public mental health, it has yet to develop the analogous tools, and the absence is consequential.

Our constructive proposal holds that the alternative is not the restoration of the 'biomedical' monopoly but the genuine plurality of evidence-based approaches, within the realm of scientific evidence, enforced by voluntary association and exit rights, rather than by editorial monoculture and institutional expulsion ritual.

This is an anti-antipsychiatric Perspective. It defends psychiatry, and the ethos of psychiatry, its honour, against a specific register that has claimed its harshest critics for itself while having little to do with the actual tradition of patient-led reform from which serious criticism of psychiatry has historically come. Reil, who coined the discipline two hundred years ago and demanded that its practitioners meet the patient as *primus inter pares*, would not recognise the abolition register as a continuation of his project. Beers would not have countersigned the Jackman piece. Laing would not have countersigned the Ferreira essay. Jamison and Linehan do not require translation into the contemporary movement's vocabulary in order to count as authentic voices of lived-experience in mental health. A recovery of the tradition Reil named, Beers built, Laing practised, and Jamison and Linehan continue is, in our submission, overdue.

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